

FAAM facility for airborne atmospheric measurements

FLIGHT FOLDER

Flight No. B364
Date: 07 May 2008
Take Off: 13:28:00Z
Landing: 15:50:48Z
Flight Time 2h 23m

Campaign: EUCAARI

Operating Area: Rotterdam – Melpitz - Oberpfaffenhofen

POB	Position	Name	Institute	Logs y/n
1	Captain	Alan Foster	Directflight	
2	Co-pilot	Ian Ramsay-Rae	Directflight	
3	CCM1	Dawn Quinn	Directflight	
4	Mission Scientist 1	Keith Bower	University of Reading	
5	Flight Manager	Alan Woolley	FAAM	
6	CCN / CCM2	Jamie Trembath	FAAM	
7	Cloud Physics	Jim Crawford	FAAM	
8	Wet & Dry Neph / PSAP / Filters / CVI	James Bowles	Met Office	
9	SWS	Debbie O'Sullivan	Met Office	
10	AMS	Paul Williams	University of Manchester	
11	2D-S / CAPS / CPI	Dantong Liu	University of Manchester	
12	Core Chem	Mo Smith	FAAM	
13	Mission Scientist 2	Hugh Coe	University of Manchester	
14	CCN Training	Steve Cowan	FAAM	

Flight Track:

B364 Track 07-MAY-08

FLIGHT SUMMARY

Flight No B364
 Date: 7/5/08
 Project: EUCAARI
 Location: NDG/Memmingham (PCASP Test)

Start Time	End Time	Event	Height (s)	Hdg	Comments
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131003		Start-Up	1.7 kft	359	
131602		Taxy	1.7 kft	359	
131711		ASP	1.7 kft	359	open
132256	132559	Pirouette 1	1.7 kft	359	
132800		T/O	1.7 kft	359	
133248		jw/nevz zero	7.0 kft	359	
133331		lwr bbr	7.0 kft	359	exposed
133826	134119	Profile 1	6.9 - 3.9 kft	359	
134220	135236	Run 1.1	3.9 kft	359	
135557	140608	Run 1.2	3.9 kft	359	
140608	140711	Profile 2	3.9 - 4.9 kft	359	
140913	141023	Profile 2	4.8 - 6.0 kft	359	resumed
141059	142121	Run 2.1	6.0 kft	359	
142404	143413	Run 2.2	6.0 kft	359	
143606	144354	Profile 3	6.0 - 14.0 kft	359	
144527	144639	Profile 3	14.0 - 15.0 kft	359	resumed
144640	145634	Run 3.1	15.0 kft	359	
144910		jw nevz zero	15.0 kft	359	
145951	150510	Profile 4	15.0 - 20.0 kft	359	
151209	152207	Run 4.1	20.0 kft	359	
152339	153308	Run 4.2	20.1 - 20.0 kft	359	
155048		Land	1.8 kft	359	
155239	155530	Pirouette 2	1.7 kft	359	
160017		Shutdown	1.7 kft	359	

B364 Track 07-MAY-08

EUCAARI Test Flight B364
FAAM sortie brief

Wednesday 7th May, 2008

1. Pilot 1 (Directflight) – Alan Foster
2. Pilot 2 (Directflight) – Ian Ramsay-Rae
3. CCM (Directflight) – Dawn Quinn
4. Core Chemistry - Maureen Smith (FAAM)
5. Flight Manager – Alan Woolley (FAAM)
6. CCN – Jamie Trembath (FAAM)
7. AMS – Paul Williams (Manchester)
8. Cloud Physics – Jim Crawford (FAAM)
9. SP2 – Dantong Liu (Manchester)
10. SWS/SHIMS – Debbie O’Sullivan (Met Office)
11. Wet Neph – James Bowles (Met Office)
12. Mission Scientist – Keith Bower (Manchester)
13. Mission Scientist – Claire McConnell (Reading)
14. CCN Training – Steve Cowan (FAAM)

Operating Area:

Southern Germany, between Memmingen and NDG (Nordlingen Beacon)

Sortie Objectives:

Intercomparison of FAAM and DLR PCASP instruments with both mounted on BAe146. Perform a series of SLRs at various altitudes within and above aerosol.

Weather.

Forecast predicts weak flow from the southeast around high pressure system located over Scandanavia/Denmark. Clear skies preferred.

Key Instruments

PCASP instruments, cloud physics.

Flight patterns:

1. Given clear skies (no clouds to interfere with direct radiation) prior to take-off perform pirouette on the runway. (360 degree turn, at around 120 degrees per minute).
2. Take off Oberpfaffenhofen at 1300z (1500 local)
3. Transit to at 5kft asl to Memmingen, descending to 4kft asl at Memmingen.
[11 mins, T=11]
4. SLR at 4kft asl (2kft agl) from Memmingen to NDG, reciprocal turn, and SLR from NDG back to Memmingen
[15+14=29 mins, T=40]
5. Profile at 1000ft/min to 6kft asl and turn towards NDG [4 mins, T=44]

6. Repeat point 5 at 6kft (4kft agl) [13+13=26 mins, T=70]
7. Reciprocal turn towards NDG and profile to FL150 at 1000ft/min ending above NDG [13 mins, T=83]
8. SLR at FL150 from NDG to Memmingen to NDG [12+13=25, T=108]
9. Profile to FL250 at 1000ft/min ending above Memmingen [10 mins, T=118]
10. SLRs at FL250 from Memmingen to NDG and back to Memmingen [25mins, T=143]
11. return to Oberpfaffenhofen [10 mins, T=153]
12. Given clear skies (no clouds to interfere with direct radiation) upon landing perform pirouette on the runway. (360 degree turn, at around 120 degrees per minute).

Other comments:

Mission Scientist's Debrief Sheet

Flight B364

7th May 2008

Summary of the weather conditions:

Atlantic low positioned to the southwest of Iceland (996 mbar) and High (1025mbar) centred in the eastern North sea to the west of Denmark, extending north to cover the SW of Norway.

The flight was carried out in the weak anticyclonic flow around the North Sea High, producing gentle easterly/ ESE flow in the military box area to the west of OB. Skies were generally clear although there were some isolated puffs of fair weather clouds between 6 and 10kft asl.

Operating Area:

Southern Germany in the Allgau military box area to the west of Oberpfaffenhofen (OP above), specifically between two way points at Memmingen (Mem) and NDG (Nordlinginen Beacon).

Summary of the flight:

A successful flight was carried out intercomparing the FAAM and DLR PCASP instruments (mounted outboard and inboard respectively on the portside pylon of BAe146 aircraft) along a series of SLRs at various altitudes within and above the aerosol filled boundary layer. The operator reported both probes following similar concentration trends although the DLR probe was being logged on a PMS interface not usually used for PCASP instruments and so the magnitude of the concentrations reported were not corrected for a as yet unknown calibration factor (realtime). Upon application of this scaling factor further intercomparison of the total number concentrations and more specifically the size dependant concentrations will be required to assess the variations between and the suitability of the pylon mounting positions for this probe (NB a laboratory intercomparison of these probes was undertaken at the DLR labs earlier in the year and showed close agreement between the two instruments).

The aircraft transited to the box area at 7kft and carried out a profile descent into the box to the 4kft asl level at Memmingen (Mem). An SLR was carried out at this level to NDG, followed by the reciprocal leg back to Mem. CPC concentrations varied between 5000 and 10000 cm⁻³ with a few peaks >10,000cm⁻³. (up to 15000cm⁻³). The AMS reported seeing ~3µg m⁻³ of sulphate nitrate and organic on the first leg. CAS reported concentrations up to 200cm⁻³ (in the 0.6-0.8µm range). The SP2 reported a lot of black carbon (BC) with high scattering near to the end of R1.1 (Nordlinginen). Also towards the end of the run two power station plumes were observed off to the right hand side (RHS) - or east of the aircraft which appeared to influence the measurements (eg CAPs reported picking up the plume as 1 to a few µm particles). The Nephelometer reported similar scattering pattern on both R1 legs, the scattering being

highest (around 55 m-1 for the blue channel) midway along the runs and slightly higher at the southern end. At one point a high CCN fraction was reported at the time of low total counts.

A profile ascent was undertaken during the turn and repositioning for the next set of SLRs at FL60. The AMS and WCPC were fitted with a filter and the WCPC was found not to be zeroing during P2, indicating the presence of a small leak. During R2.1 to NDG, an attempt was made to fly through a small puffy cloud. The captain described this as appearing to form in the outflow from the power station, and that this cloud as a result had a lower cloud base than similar clouds that were also present in the area. Cloud tops of the surrounding fair weather Cu were around 10kft. Towards the end of the run, the CCN was described as crashing (an unfortunate turn of phrase in an aircraft) which meant the activated fraction (the activated number as a fraction of total CN) dramatically fell off at this time. Again on the leg south (R2.2) the CCN exhibited the same trend whereby the number of CCN increased relative to the total CN concentration. Other parameters showed similar N-S gradients, particularly the Nephelometer. There was a dramatic and sharp 40% reduction in scattering at the northern end of R2.1, while CN showed a converse sharp (almost four fold) increase in number at the NDG end (explaining the “crash” in CCN activated fraction) (see below R2.1 14:11-14:21, R2.2 14:24-14:34). NOx concentrations increased more towards the middle of the run but were generally higher overall during R2.2. O3 also showed this trend of enhanced concentrations during R2.2 compared to R2.1. These changes may indicate variations in the BL height going from N to S and possibly the effect of BL pumping through clouds and convection in general.

After turning at Mem, P3 up to a FL140 commenced heading north to NDG. CN aerosol concentrations and aerosol scattering fell away almost as soon as the ascent started indicating the top of the BL at around FL60. NOx previously around 3-5ppb also fell off to around zero (≤ 0.5 ppb) while O3 decreased dramatically from 55-60ppb to around 40ppb. CO also decreased from around 220ppb (on average) to around 170ppb. The profile was interrupted at FL140 at NDG to turn, and recommenced until achieving FL150, when R3.1 N-S was undertaken at that level. After overshooting Mem and turning, a final profile ascent up to FL200 was undertaken heading north towards NDG. Two further runs R4.1 and 4.2 were undertaken in a NW-SE orientation (121 and 300deg). As expected both PCASPs showed only residual counts at these higher levels.

Instrumentation - Please see FAAM folder

Mission Scientist's Log

Flight No **B.3364** Date 07/05/08 Name K.N. BOWER Page 1 of 3

(13:22:56)

GMT	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks (clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)
					(km) 1021 17°/5°
15.10	KNB / time	15.11.22 / 15.11.58	15.12.11		1st engine start, 2 nd , 3 rd , 4 th
					060°/8kts R/W 22 in T/W E
15.23.32	KNB			Start	Pirouette
15.26.35	KNB			End	Pirouette.
15.28.06	KNB				Rolling on R/W 22.
15.28.35	KNB				T/D
15.30.27	KNB	5000ft			
13.35.50	≡ 36	28 KNB		(KNB = HD 220E + 35)	Time check
13:38.18	P1 ↓	start			Descent into box area in transit (no SMPs)
13.41.18	P1 end	3800	272	47°54'/10°12'	879mb 9.56/1.79
13.42.19	R1.1	3800	22	48°/10°6'	878mb 9.8/1.67 (150) (359)
	R1.1	"			AMS ✓ sees 3/3/3 NO ₂ /CO ₂ /O ₃ (μg/m ³)
	R1.1	"			PIASPS - same trend - diff scaling factor
					CAS - up to 200/cm ² 0.61-0.8μ
					SP2 - not a lot of BC
					CON - nice time ↑ 0.2 ↑ fraction activated
					No ↓
					CON
					Power Stir's: 2 cooling tower plumes 48-49
					CON μg AMS
13.50					SP2 - lot BC - scattering ↑ too.
13.52.28	R1.1 end	3800	12°	48°36'/10°18'	8.35/-0.02 107mb (359) 878mb
					CO Cal in turn
					CIP saw plume - UPS + 1 μm - fan

Mission Scientist's Log

Flight No **B364**... Date **7/5/08**... Name **K.N.B**... Page **2** of **3**

GMT	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks (clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)
13 55 55	R1.2 st	3.9 kft	177	48°36'/10°18'	8.94°/-0.45° 108 m/s 880 mb low total counts; high CN fraction
14.00.05	R1.2 end	3.9 kft	187	48°0'/10°12'	CP2 875 mb. 9.55°/1.03° 112 m/s
14.06.08	P2 start				CEN Regel on CP2
14:07.11	P2 Int				
14:09.13	P2 recd	4.9 kft			Neph - similar on both legs of previous runs.
14. 11. 00	P2 End / R2.1 st	FL60		48°0'/10°12'	811 mb 3.55°/0.16° 111 m/s
14. 13.00	R2.1		10		AMS - Altz which with CPC not zeroing PCAsps - tracking well FAAM 1000/cc CAsps ✓ CAS 1st couple of channels 0-100/oz
14. 19. 10 (12)	R2.1	FL60	2	48°30'/10°18'	Through little patch cloud - Capt sees :- as in Power of outflow - lower CB than all others
14: 21. 21	R2.1 end				CEN crack - test CN Fraction of CN
14. 24. 03	R2.2 st	FL60	189	48°42'/10°24'	CT ~ 10000 - grey below, 810 mb 2.54°/-0.31° CCN & CN low - some pattern on this run. - Altz NEPT - N-S gradient
14. 34. 11	R2.2 end	FL60	187	48°6'/10°12'	811 mb 3.45°/-0.5° 111 m/s.
14 36.06	P3 st	initially 4	9500	48°6'/10°18'	14.18 - manually set assigned. 25 → 105 m/s
14 43 54	P3 int		12°		OIC - left Ao behind - Neph ↓ O3 ↓ CN ↓
14.45.28	P3 rec	FL140	187		
14.46.37	P3 end / R3.1 st	FL150		48°30'/10°12'	st 571 mb, -13.16°/-25.41° 142 m/s.
14.56.33	R3.1 end	FL150	190	47°42'/10°6'	-12.42°/-27.12° 571 mb. 127 m/s.

CLOUD PHYSICS LOG Flight B

Date: 07 may 08	Operator: JC	DRS Time:	DAU1 Time:	DAU2 Time:	DAU3 Time:	Aux1 Time:	Aux2 Time:	Page 1 of 1
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G.M.T	PCASP		FFSSP	SID1	SID2	2D2-C		2D2-P		CIP25			CIP100			Habit	Remarks
	Conc/cc	Mean R	Block TX	Count	Count	Conc/L	Max size	Conc/m3	Max size	Conc m3	Max size	LWC	Conc m3	Max size	LWC		
	DFVLR PCASP fitted to port inboard upper, replacing 2DP Note: cmd1d 0 3 command required to start pump Probe power is on switch 4 & not interlocked Heater power is controlled by 28V switch – on only when airborne																
	13:10 ffssp running, recording on sid1 b364-1.srd pcasp faam pump running, heater off vref 7.8v pcasp dfvlr pump running, heater off vref 3.2v 2dc running																
132256																Pirouette on threshold for radistion instruments	
132800																T/O, heaters on	
123826																Start p1	
133900	1000	0.09	1	3		0	0										
134100	10000	0.09	1	3		0	0									End p1	
134220																Start r 1,1	
134300	500	0.09	1	3		0	0										
134500	700	0.09	2	3		0	0										
134700	1100	0.09	2	3		0	0										
134900	1200	0.09	2	3		0	0										
135030	1400	0.09	2	3		0	0									Power station	
135200	1000	0.09	2	3		0	0										
135236																End run 1.1	
135600	1000	0.09	2	3		0	0									Start run 1.2	
135800	1200	0.09	2	3		0	0										
140000	1400	0.09	2	3		0	0										
140200	1000	0.09	2	3		0	0										
140400	570	0.09	3	3		0	0										
140600	800	0.09	3	3		0	0									End run 1.2 start profile 2	
140800	700	0.09	3	3		0	0										
141000	500	0.09	3	3		0	0									End p2	

PCASP Reference Volts =	FFSSP Reference Volts =	2D2-C End element 1 voltage =	CIP25 End element 1 voltage =	CIP100 End element 1 voltage =
PCASP Flow rate =		2D2-C End element 32 voltage =	CIP25 End element 64 voltage =	CIP100 End element 64 voltage =
© Met Office 2007	SID2 Laser power =	2D2-P End element 1 voltage =		

CLOUD PHYSICS LOG Flight B

Date: 07 may 08	Operator: JC	DRS Time:	DAU1 Time:	DAU2 Time:	DAU3 Time:	Aux1 Time:	Aux2 Time:	Page 2 of 2
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G.M.T	PCASP		FFSSP	SID1	SID2	2D2-C		2D2-P		CIP25			CIP100			Habit	Remarks
	Conc/cc	Mean R	Block TX	Count	Count	Conc/L	Max size	Conc/m3	Max size	Conc m3	Max size	LWC	Conc m3	Max size	LWC		
141105	400	0.09	3	3		0	0									Start run 2.1	
141300	900	0.09	3	3		0	0										
141500	1000	0.09	3	3		0	0										
141700	1300	0.09	3	3		0	0										
1411900	1200	0.09	7	3		0	0										
141730				1000												Cloud	
142100	1000	0.09	7	3		0	0										
142130																End run 2.1	
142400	1100	0.09	7	3		0	0									Start run 2.2	
142600	900	0.09	7	3		0	0										
142800	1300	0.09	7	3		0	0										
143000	1200	0.09	7	3		0	0										
143200	900	0.09	7	3		0	0										
143400	600	0.09	7	3		0	0									End run 2.2	
143606	720	0.09	7	3		0	0									Start profile 3	
143800	60	0.09	8	1		0	0										
144000	50	0.09	8	1		0	0										
144200	10	0.09	8	1		0	0										
144400	7	0.09	8	1		0	0										
144600	4	0.09	8	0		0	0									End p3	
144700	15	0.09	8	0		0	0									Run 3.1	
144900	22		8	0		0	0										
145100	14		8	0		0	0										
145300	10		8	0		0	0										
145500	14		9	0		0	0										
145600																End r 3.1	
145951																Start p4	
150000	15		9	0		0	0										
150200	4		9	0		0	0										
150400	10		9	0		0	0										
150500																End p4	
150800	15		9	0		0	0										
151000	18		9	0		0	0										
151200	18		9	0		0	0									Run 4.1	
151400	16		9	0		0	0										
151600	15		9	0		0	0										
151800	18		9	0		0	0										

PCASP Reference Volts =	FFSSP Reference Volts =	2D2-C End element 1 voltage =	CIP25 End element 1 voltage =	CIP100 End element 1 voltage =
PCASP Flow rate =		2D2-C End element 32 voltage =	CIP25 End element 64 voltage =	CIP100 End element 64 voltage =
© Met Office 2007	SID2 Laser power =	2D2-P End element 1 voltage =		

B364_SWS_SHIMS_EventLog.txt

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11:29:28.55 --- - - - -
11:29:28.55 --- - - - - +++ SOFTWARE START/RESTART +++
11:29:28.55 --- - - - - +++ hh:mm:ss.ff / Instr / Posn / Period /
tVIS/ tNIR / Comment +++
11:29:28.55 --- - - - - +++ Flight no. B364
11:29:28.55 --- - - - -
11:29:37.83 SWS - - - - Telescope motor initialised.
11:29:49.29 SWS 0.0 - - - - Telescope sent to -6.000
11:29:49.84 SWS -6.0 - - - - Telescope stopped.
11:29:58.98 SWS -6.0 - - - - Telescope sent to 174.000
11:30:00.64 SWS 170.4 - - - - Telescope stopped.
11:30:18.37 SWS - - - - Initialization: VIS OK NIR OK
11:30:18.46 USH - - - - Initialization: VIS OK NIR OK
11:30:18.55 LSH - - - - Initialization: VIS OK NIR OK
11:30:42.34 SWS - 100 - - - - Sample period changed from 250ms to 100ms.
11:30:44.48 USH - 100 - - - - Sample period changed from 250ms to 100ms.
11:30:48.08 LSH - 100 - - - - Sample period changed from 250ms to 100ms.
11:46:21.95 SWS - - - - 5 NIR int.time changed from 5ms to 5ms.
11:46:23.52 USH - - - - 5 NIR int.time changed from 5ms to 5ms.
11:46:25.35 LSH - - - - 5 NIR int.time changed from 5ms to 5ms.
11:46:30.41 LSH - - 400 - - VIS int.time changed from 5ms to 400ms.
11:46:30.42 LSH - - - 400 - - NIR int.time changed from 5ms to 400ms.
11:46:34.32 USH - - 100 - - VIS int.time changed from 5ms to 100ms.
11:46:34.32 USH - - - 100 - - NIR int.time changed from 5ms to 100ms.
11:46:38.71 SWS - - 100 - - VIS int.time changed from 5ms to 100ms.
11:46:38.72 SWS - - - 100 - - NIR int.time changed from 5ms to 100ms.
11:46:41.47 SWS - - - - Manual scene recording started.
11:46:41.47 LSH - - - - Manual scene recording started.
11:46:41.48 USH - - - - Manual scene recording started.
11:46:49.10 LSH - - 600 - - VIS int.time changed from 400ms to 600ms.
11:46:49.11 LSH - - - 600 - - NIR int.time changed from 400ms to 600ms.
11:46:51.66 USH - - - - Dark measurement started.
11:46:51.67 SWS - - - - Dark measurement started.
11:46:51.98 USH - - - - Warning: Abnormally bright dark measurement.
11:46:52.14 LSH - - - - Dark measurement started.
11:46:52.18 SWS - - - - Warning: Abnormally bright dark measurement.
11:46:52.97 LSH - - - - Warning: Abnormally bright dark measurement.
11:46:53.14 USH - - - - Manual scene recording started.
11:46:53.31 SWS - - - - Manual scene recording started.
11:46:54.57 --- - - - - Reset shutters.
11:46:58.60 LSH - - - - Manual scene recording started.
11:46:59.51 USH - - - - Dark measurement started.
11:47:00.94 USH - - - - Manual scene recording started.
11:47:03.15 LSH - - - - Dark measurement started.
11:47:07.15 SWS - - - - Dark measurement started.
11:47:08.58 SWS - - - - Manual scene recording started.
11:47:09.64 LSH - - - - Manual scene recording started.
11:47:54.29 SWS - - - - Warning: Clipping may be occurring.
11:58:07.94 SWS 174.0 - - - - Telescope sent to 20.000
11:58:09.61 SWS 20.0 - - - - Telescope stopped.
11:59:56.39 SWS - - - - Dark measurement started.
11:59:57.83 SWS - - - - Manual scene recording started.
12:02:40.33 USH - - - - Idling
12:02:40.35 SWS - - - - Idling
12:02:40.72 LSH - - - - Idling
12:11:38.06 SWS 20.0 - - - - Telescope sent to -6.000
12:11:41.33 SWS -6.0 - - - - Telescope sent to 174.000
12:11:43.01 SWS 171.2 - - - - Telescope stopped.
12:11:58.24 SWS 174.0 - - - - Telescope sent to 30.000
12:11:59.91 SWS 30.0 - - - - Telescope stopped.
13:07:33.95 SWS - - - - Manual scene recording started.
13:07:33.96 LSH - - - - Manual scene recording started.
13:07:33.97 USH - - - - Manual scene recording started.
13:07:36.56 USH - - - - Dark measurement started.
13:07:36.62 SWS - - - - Dark measurement started.
13:07:36.89 USH - - - - Warning: Abnormally bright dark measurement.
13:07:37.06 LSH - - - - Dark measurement started.

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13:07:37.10	SWS	-	-	-	-	Warning: Abnormally bright dark measurement.
13:07:37.88	LSH	-	-	-	-	Warning: Abnormally bright dark measurement.
13:07:38.03	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
13:07:38.22	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
13:07:39.54	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:07:41.00	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
13:07:43.14	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:07:43.47	USH	-	-	-	-	Warning: Abnormally bright dark measurement.
13:07:43.55	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
13:07:44.60	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
13:07:57.36	---	-	-	-	-	Reset shutters.
13:08:02.81	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:08:04.27	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
13:08:05.61	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:08:08.64	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:08:10.13	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
13:08:12.06	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
13:14:20.11	SWS	30.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -6.000
13:14:24.19	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:14:25.77	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
13:14:27.28	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:14:28.78	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
13:14:30.43	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:14:36.92	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
13:14:45.90	---	-	-	-	-	*** cooler at -6
13:17:00.97	---	-	-	-	-	*** pirohutte on runway clear skies
13:17:14.81	---	-	-	-	-	*** start pf piroeutte
13:22:57.61	---	-	-	-	-	*** correction start of 360 deg pirouette now
13:25:58.32	---	-	-	-	-	*** end of pirhouette 1 (sza 40.95) (SAa
232.37)						
13:28:29.97	SWS	-	-	-	-	Warning: Clipping may be occurring.
13:28:43.05	SWS	-	-	-	-	Warning: Clipping may be occurring.
13:29:20.11	---	-	-	-	-	*** cooler at -5
13:29:27.55	SWS	-	-	50	-	VIS int.time changed from 100ms to 50ms.
13:29:27.55	SWS	-	-	-	50	NIR int.time changed from 100ms to 50ms.
13:29:30.82	USH	-	-	50	-	VIS int.time changed from 100ms to 50ms.
13:29:30.83	USH	-	-	-	50	NIR int.time changed from 100ms to 50ms.
13:29:33.78	---	-	-	-	-	Reset shutters.
13:29:37.02	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:29:37.96	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
13:29:38.42	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:29:39.38	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
13:29:40.18	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:29:46.62	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
13:31:59.66	---	-	-	-	-	*** cooler at minus 4 deg
13:38:31.49	---	-	-	-	-	*** profile descent
13:41:21.74	---	-	-	-	-	*** end of p1
13:41:29.90	---	-	-	-	-	*** cooler at -5
13:42:21.95	---	-	-	-	-	*** run 1
13:48:44.46	SWS	-	-	-	-	Warning: Clipping may be occurring.
13:49:34.31	---	-	-	-	-	*** cooler at minus 6
13:52:32.71	---	-	-	-	-	*** end of run
13:55:59.36	---	-	-	-	-	*** run 1.2
13:58:44.39	---	-	-	-	-	*** cooler at -7
13:59:36.13	---	-	-	-	-	*** cooler at -6
14:04:30.29	SWS	-	-	35	-	VIS int.time changed from 50ms to 35ms.
14:04:30.30	SWS	-	-	-	35	NIR int.time changed from 50ms to 35ms.
14:04:32.83	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:04:33.63	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
14:04:37.33	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:04:38.13	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
14:04:40.37	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:04:41.33	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
14:04:43.99	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:04:50.38	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:04:50.44	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
14:04:51.39	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
14:04:52.67	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:04:53.47	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.

```

14:06:00.44 --- - - - - *** end of run 1.2
14:06:07.53 --- - - - - *** profile climb
14:06:22.70 --- - - - - *** p 2
14:07:37.99 --- - - - - *** interrupt to p2
14:09:16.31 --- - - - - *** recommence p2
14:10:26.05 --- - - - - *** end of p2 at fl 60
14:11:00.83 --- - - - - *** start of run 2 at FL 60
14:12:15.95 --- - - - - Reset shutters.
14:12:21.85 SWS - - - - Dark measurement started.
14:12:21.86 USH - - - - Dark measurement started.
14:12:22.10 LSH - - - - Dark measurement started.
14:12:22.68 SWS - - - - Manual scene recording started.
14:12:23.01 USH - - - - Manual scene recording started.
14:12:28.70 LSH - - - - Manual scene recording started.
14:12:31.52 USH - - - - Dark measurement started.
14:12:31.59 SWS - - - - Dark measurement started.
14:12:32.03 LSH - - - - Dark measurement started.
14:12:32.48 USH - - - - Manual scene recording started.
14:12:32.57 SWS - - - - Manual scene recording started.
14:12:38.49 LSH - - - - Manual scene recording started.
14:17:37.02 --- - - - - Reset shutters.
14:18:22.67 --- - - - - *** going through cloud
14:18:35.92 --- - - - - *** clear of cloud but cloud above
14:18:39.62 LSH - - - - Dark measurement started.
14:18:45.41 USH - - - - Dark measurement started.
14:18:46.08 LSH - - - - Manual scene recording started.
14:18:46.40 USH - - - - Manual scene recording started.
14:18:47.39 SWS - - - - Dark measurement started.
14:18:48.19 SWS - - - - Manual scene recording started.
14:18:50.65 LSH - - - - Dark measurement started.
14:18:54.61 USH - - - - Dark measurement started.
14:18:55.60 USH - - - - Manual scene recording started.
14:18:56.89 SWS - - - - Dark measurement started.
14:18:57.15 LSH - - - - Manual scene recording started.
14:18:57.73 SWS - - - - Manual scene recording started.
14:21:26.02 --- - - - - *** end of run
14:23:34.11 --- - - - - *** passed through some cloud
14:24:05.93 --- - - - - *** start of run
14:24:15.44 --- - - - - *** run 2.2
14:27:18.96 --- - - - - *** cooler at -5
14:29:37.78 --- - - - - Reset shutters.
14:29:45.37 LSH - - - - Dark measurement started.
14:29:50.19 USH - - - - Dark measurement started.
14:29:51.25 USH - - - - Manual scene recording started.
14:29:51.82 LSH - - - - Manual scene recording started.
14:29:55.88 SWS - - - - Dark measurement started.
14:29:56.70 SWS - - - - Manual scene recording started.
14:30:05.16 LSH - - - - Dark measurement started.
14:30:08.42 USH - - - - Dark measurement started.
14:30:09.40 USH - - - - Manual scene recording started.
14:30:11.41 SWS - - - - Dark measurement started.
14:30:11.67 LSH - - - - Manual scene recording started.
14:30:12.29 SWS - - - - Manual scene recording started.
14:30:23.16 --- - - - - *** cooler at -4
14:34:13.68 --- - - - - *** end of run 2.2
14:36:08.18 --- - - - - *** profile climb
14:36:33.89 SWS - - - - Idling
14:36:33.92 USH - - - - Idling
14:36:34.14 LSH - - - - Idling
14:36:37.03 SWS -6.0 - - - - Telescope sent to 174.000
14:36:38.75 SWS 173.8 - - - - Telescope stopped.
14:36:40.76 USH - - - - Manual scene recording started.
14:36:40.77 LSH - - - - Manual scene recording started.
14:36:40.77 SWS - - - - Manual scene recording started.
14:36:44.99 --- - - - - Reset shutters.
14:36:50.03 SWS - - - - Dark measurement started.
14:36:50.07 USH - - - - Dark measurement started.
14:36:50.35 LSH - - - - Dark measurement started.
14:36:50.86 SWS - - - - Manual scene recording started.

```

14:36:51.20	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
14:36:54.08	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:36:54.16	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:36:54.88	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
14:36:55.27	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
14:36:56.92	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
14:37:02.78	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:37:09.25	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
14:38:13.92	---	-	-	-	-	*** cooler at -5 deg
14:38:30.76	---	-	-	-	-	Reset shutters.
14:38:35.34	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:38:36.17	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
14:38:37.58	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:38:38.56	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
14:38:40.67	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:38:47.11	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
14:41:59.37	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:42:00.21	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
14:42:01.75	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:42:02.86	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
14:42:04.30	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:42:11.48	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
14:44:27.64	---	-	-	-	-	*** interupt profile
14:44:58.16	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:44:59.04	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
14:44:59.37	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
14:45:00.18	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:45:01.21	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
14:45:02.82	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:45:09.56	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
14:45:24.41	---	-	-	-	-	*** cooler at -6
14:45:31.76	---	-	-	-	-	*** recomencce profile
14:46:35.92	---	-	-	-	-	*** end of p3
14:46:51.84	---	-	-	-	-	*** start of run 3.1
14:53:55.89	---	-	-	-	-	*** cooler at -7
14:56:43.72	---	-	-	-	-	*** cooler at -6
14:57:38.77	---	-	-	-	-	*** run 3.1 ended at 14 46??
15:02:48.31	---	-	-	-	-	Reset shutters.
15:02:53.56	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
15:02:53.57	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
15:02:53.62	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
15:02:54.54	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
15:02:54.77	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
15:03:00.25	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
15:05:05.08	---	-	-	-	-	*** end of profile climb
15:07:21.35	---	-	-	-	-	Reset shutters.
15:07:29.89	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
15:07:29.94	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
15:07:30.39	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
15:07:30.73	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
15:07:31.09	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
15:07:36.88	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
15:08:35.46	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
15:08:36.27	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
15:08:37.52	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
15:08:38.47	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
15:08:39.61	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
15:08:46.08	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
15:22:13.26	---	-	-	-	-	*** end of run
15:22:19.15	---	-	-	-	-	*** run 4.1
15:22:56.71	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
15:22:56.76	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
15:22:57.12	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
15:23:01.16	SWS	174.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -6.000
15:23:02.89	SWS	-5.6	-	-	-	Telescope stopped.
15:23:04.42	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
15:23:04.43	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
15:23:04.44	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
15:23:51.71	---	-	-	-	-	*** start of run

```

15:23:59.67 --- - - - - *** run 4.2?
15:25:07.13 --- - - - - Reset shutters.
15:25:12.23 USH - - - - Dark measurement started.
15:25:12.33 SWS - - - - Dark measurement started.
15:25:12.62 LSH - - - - Dark measurement started.
15:25:13.22 USH - - - - Manual scene recording started.
15:25:13.33 SWS - - - - Manual scene recording started.
15:25:19.14 LSH - - - - Manual scene recording started.
15:25:22.52 USH - - - - Dark measurement started.
15:25:22.56 SWS - - - - Dark measurement started.
15:25:23.11 LSH - - - - Dark measurement started.
15:25:23.54 SWS - - - - Manual scene recording started.
15:25:23.61 USH - - - - Manual scene recording started.
15:25:29.58 LSH - - - - Manual scene recording started.
15:26:27.81 SWS - - - 50 - VIS int.time changed from 35ms to 50ms.
15:26:27.82 SWS - - - 50 - NIR int.time changed from 35ms to 50ms.
15:26:30.04 SWS - - - - Dark measurement started.
15:26:31.07 SWS - - - - Manual scene recording started.
15:26:34.86 SWS - - - - Dark measurement started.
15:26:35.85 SWS - - - - Manual scene recording started.
15:27:00.81 --- - - - - Reset shutters.
15:27:05.76 SWS - - - - Dark measurement started.
15:27:05.84 USH - - - - Dark measurement started.
15:27:05.90 LSH - - - - Dark measurement started.
15:27:06.76 SWS - - - - Manual scene recording started.
15:27:06.95 USH - - - - Manual scene recording started.
15:27:07.00 LSH - - - - Dark measurement started.
15:27:13.61 LSH - - - - Idling
15:32:16.76 LSH - - - - Manual scene recording started.
15:32:55.90 --- - - - - Reset shutters.
15:33:00.51 --- - - - - Reset shutters.
15:33:05.84 SWS - - - - Dark measurement started.
15:33:06.89 SWS - - - - Manual scene recording started.
15:33:09.53 USH - - - - Dark measurement started.
15:33:10.63 USH - - - - Manual scene recording started.
15:33:14.47 --- - - - - *** end of run
15:33:23.86 LSH - - - - Dark measurement started.
15:33:30.32 LSH - - - - Manual scene recording started.
15:34:11.84 SWS - - - 40 - VIS int.time changed from 50ms to 40ms.
15:34:11.85 SWS - - - 40 - NIR int.time changed from 50ms to 40ms.
15:34:14.05 SWS - - - - Dark measurement started.
15:34:14.91 SWS - - - - Manual scene recording started.
15:34:16.49 SWS - - - - Dark measurement started.
15:34:17.33 SWS - - - - Manual scene recording started.
15:52:03.03 --- - - - - *** landed
15:52:26.93 --- - - - - *** cooler temp -5
15:52:41.80 --- - - - - *** pirhouette 2
15:53:47.49 --- - - - - *** sza 64.31
15:53:56.02 --- - - - - *** saa 267.38
15:54:04.69 --- - - - - *** cooler temp -4
15:54:18.97 --- - - - - *** cooler temp
15:54:21.87 --- - - - - *** -3
15:55:30.99 --- - - - - *** end of pirohette 2
15:55:38.93 --- - - - - Reset shutters.
15:55:44.52 USH - - - - Dark measurement started.
15:55:44.58 SWS - - - - Dark measurement started.
15:55:45.03 LSH - - - - Dark measurement started.
15:55:45.48 USH - - - - Manual scene recording started.
15:55:45.66 SWS - - - - Manual scene recording started.
15:55:51.60 LSH - - - - Manual scene recording started.
15:55:55.57 USH - - - - Dark measurement started.
15:55:55.65 LSH - - - - Dark measurement started.
15:55:55.68 SWS - - - - Dark measurement started.
15:55:56.62 USH - - - - Manual scene recording started.
15:55:56.86 SWS - - - - Manual scene recording started.
15:56:02.30 LSH - - - - Manual scene recording started.
15:58:34.78 --- - - - - *** cooler temp at -3
16:00:59.81 SWS - - - - Telescope disabled.

```


Flight:

B364

KEY

Not Fitted

Fitted, Not Operated

Duff Data

Minor Problems

OK

Thermometers

Cabin Temperature:

Heimann:

Deiced Temp:

Non-deiced Temp:

Hygrometers

FWVS:

Buck CR2:

General Eastern:

Johnson Williams:

Nevzorov:

Total Water Probe:

Cameras

Downward Facing:

Forward Facing:

Rearward Facing:

Upward Facing:

Navigation + Aircraft

Cruciform GPS:

GIN Applanix:

INU Honeywell:

Radar Altimeter:

RVSM IAS:

RVSM Static Pressure:

XR5 GPS:

Misc Core

AMTG:

AVAPS:

Cabin Pressure:

Fax machine:

Printer:

S9 Static Pressure:

Satcom C:

Satcom H:

Turb Centre-Static:

Turb Left Right:

Turb Up-Down:

Turb Horizontal Chk:

Turb Vertical Chk:

Weather Radar:

DLUs:

DLU AERACK:

DLU BBR Lower:

DLU BBR Upper:

DLU Core Chem:

DLU Core Consoles:

DLU Port Aft:

DLU Port Fwd:

DLU Stbd Fwd:

Radiometers

Lower:

BBR (clear) Lower:

BBR (IR) Lower:

BBR (red) Lower:

Upper:

BBR (clear) Upper:

BBR (IR) Upper:

BBR (red) Upper:

ARIES:

DEIMOS:

IR Camera:

JNO2 Lower:

JNO2 Upper:

JO1D Lower:

JO1D Upper:

MARSS:

SHIMS Lower:

SHIMS Upper:

SWS:

TAFTS:

Cloud Probes

2DC:

2DP:

FFSSP:

PCASP:

2DS:

ADA:

CAPS:

CCN:

CDP:

CIP 100:

CIP 25:

CPI:

CVI:

SID1:

SID2:

Aerosol

CPC 3025A:

CPC 3786 H2O:

Filters 47mm:

Filters 90mm:

Neph - Dry:

Neph - Wet:

PSAP:

AMS:

CPC 3025 (AMS):

INC:

VACC:

CPC 3010A (CVI):

SP2:

UHSAS:

Chemistry

CO Aerolaser 5002:

NOx TE42C:

Ozone TE49C:

Ozone TE49:

SO2 TE43C:

TDLAS (NIR) CH4:

TDLAS (NIR) CO2:

FAGE:

Formaldehyde:

NOx FAAM:

NOxy:

ORAC:

PAN:

PERCA:

Peroxide:

PTRMS:

TDLAS (1C):

WAS Bags:

WAS Bottles:

Misc Non-Core

CASI/ATM:

LIDAR:

LTI:

SAW Hygrometer:

Faults / Incidents Log

Flight No. B364

Date: 07 May 2008

Instruments

1. INU – not responding to serial commands. Left INU off
2. FFC – smudges on camera window appeared in flight, probably insects – inform Avalon post-flight.

Instrument Status roundup

Aircraft

1. Floor around CCN position has been rucked up by operators
- 2.

ISDN Emails

Satcom-H Calls

Nil

Issues

Post Flight - Turb Probe Water Traps

1. Indicate Amount of Water: a) Nil b) 1-2 drops c) ¼ full or more d) Ice present
2. Emptied by:
3. Dried by

Transit to box at FL70

P1 descent into box area

Flight B364 13:40:39
Heading 271 deg Speed 209 knots Height 4.3kft Press 863mb
Lat 47°54.0'N Long 10°12.0'E Wind 107 ms-1/359 deg
Temp 8.31C Dewpoint 1.84C
From 13:03:31 to now

Current values

++++	STATIC PRESSURE	863.61	mb
++++	DEICED TRUE AIR TEMP	8.32	deg C
++++	DEW POINT	1.85	deg C

Plot - Microsoft Internet Explorer

Flight B364 13:41:25
Heading 272 deg Speed 207 knots Height 3.8kft Press 879mb
Lat 47°54.0'N Long 10°12.0'E Wind 106 ms-1/ 359 deg
Temp 9.86C Dewpoint 1.74C

Alt From: 13:11:25 To: now last 30 mins plot parameters as Alt

X 515.TIME FROM MIDNIGHT (secs)

573.DEW POINT (FLUORESCENCE WVS) (deg C)
574.OZONE MIXING RATIO (ppb)
575.RADAR HEIGHT (ft)
576.STATIC PRESSURE (mb)
577.PITOT STATIC PRESSURE (mb)
578.PRESSURE HEIGHT (m)
579.PRESSURE HEIGHT (Kft)

Y1 579.PRESSURE HEIGHT (Kft) Black
Y2

Just after end P1

R1.1

R1.1

Near end R1.1

Plot - Microsoft Internet Explorer

Flight B364 13:52:27
Heading 12 deg Speed 209 knots Height 3.8kft Press 878mb
Lat 48°36.0'N Long 10°18.0'E Wind 107 ms-1/ 359 deg
Temp 8.35C Dewpoint -0.02C

CO Plot From: 13:22:27 To: now last 30 mins

Save plot parameters as CO

X 515.TIME FROM MIDNIGHT (secs)

584.UPPER VISIBLE FLUX (W m-2)
585.NET INFRA-RED FLUX (W m-2)
586.UPPER NEAR INFRA-RED FRACTION (-)
587.LOWER NEAR INFRA-RED FRACTION (-)
588.CO MIXING RATIO (ppb)
589.REFRACTIVITY (Munits)
590.CORRECTED SURFACE TEMP (deg C)
591.DEWPOINT (TOTAL WATER) (deg C)

Y1 588.CO MIXING RATIO (ppb) Black Line Del
Y2

End R1.1

Start R1.2

R1.2

New plot, same times

Flight B364 14:03:07
Heading 187 deg Speed 197 knots Height 3.8kft Press 879mb
Lat 48°12.0'N Long 10°12.0'E Wind 101 ms-1/ 359 deg
Temp 9.58C Dewpoint 1.04C
From 13:32:57 to now

Current values
TIME FROM MIDNIGHT 50586 secs All sc
OZONE MIXING RATIO 3.64 ppb

New plot, same times

Flight B364 14:03:45
Heading 186 deg Speed 213 knots Height 3.8kft Press 878mb
Lat 48°6.0'N Long 10°12.0'E Wind 109 ms-1/ 359 deg
Temp 9.58C Dewpoint 1.58C
From 13:14:55 to now

Current values
TIME FROM MIDNIGHT 50625 secs All sc
CO MIXING RATIO 216.56 ppb

Flight B364 14:06:09

Heading 187 deg Speed 218 knots Height 3.9kft Press 875mb
Lat 48°0.0'N Long 10°12.0'E Wind 112 ms-1/ 359 deg
Temp 9.55C Dewpoint 1.63C

Neph BSP Plot From: 13:36:08 To: now last 30 mins

Save plot parameters as Neph BSP

X 515.TIME FROM MIDNIGHT (secs)

- 622.NEPH BLUE SP (m-1)
- 623.NEPH GREEN SP (m-1)
- 624.NEPH RED SP (m-1)
- 625.NEPH BLUE BSP (m-1)
- 626.NEPH GREEN BSP (m-1)
- 627.NEPH RED BSP (m-1)
- 628.NEPH HUMIDITY (%)

Y1 625.NEPH BLUE BSP (m-1) Black Line Del

Y2 626.NEPH GREEN BSP (m-1) Red Line Del

End P2

During R2.1

R2.1 thro base of puffy cloud

R2.2 Start

R2.2 at FL60

Interesting - lower at end of last run S-N, CCN frac of CN higher too

Near end R2.2

End R2.2

P3 start

New plot, same times

Flight B364 14:42:48
 Heading 13 deg Speed 257 knots Height 12.8kft Press 624mb
 Lat 48°30.0'N Long 10°18.0'E Wind 132 ms-1/ 359 deg
 Temp -8.01C Dewpoint -18.28C
 From 13:34:38 to now

Current values
 TIME FROM MIDNIGHT 52968 secs All sc
 — NEPH BLUE SP 1.36 m-1
 — NEPH GREEN SP 1.51 m-1
 — NEPH RED SP 1.42 m-1

New plot, same times

Flight B364 14:43:39
 Heading 10 deg Speed 249 knots Height 13.7kft Press 602mb
 Lat 48°36.0'N Long 10°18.0'E Wind 128 ms-1/ 359 deg
 Temp -9.97C Dewpoint -20.33C
 From 14:09:56 to now

Current values
 TIME FROM MIDNIGHT 53019 secs All sc
 — OZONE MIXING RATIO 42.4 ppb

New plot, same times

Flight B364 14:45:02
Heading 202 deg Speed 263 knots Height 14.2kft Press 590mb
Lat 48°36.0'N Long 10°18.0'E Wind 135 ms-1/ 359 deg
Temp -11.39C Dewpoint -22.06C
From 13:14:55 to now

Current values
TIME FROM MIDNIGHT 53100 secs All sc
CO MIXING RATIO 169.8 pbb

After P3 recc (at FL140)

Just after R3.1 start at FL150

R3.1 FL150

R3.1 FL150

New plot, same times

Flight B364 14:52:27
Heading 188 deg Speed 245 knots Height 15.0kft Press 571mb
Lat 48°0.0'N Long 10°12.0'E Wind 126 ms-1/359 deg
Temp -12.8C Dewpoint -24.56C
From 13:14:55 to now

Current values
— TIME FROM MIDNIGHT 53547 secs All sc
CO MIXING RATIO 164.56 pbb

End run R3.1 FL150

P4 start

Flight Summary B364

Event	Start	Hdg	Hgt	Lat	Long	Stop	Hdg	Hgt	Lat	Long	Comment
Start-Up	13:10:03	359	1.7kft	48.1N	11.3E						
Taxy	13:16:02	359	1.7kft	48.1N	11.3E						
ASP	13:17:11	359	1.7kft	48.1N	11.3E						open
Pirouette 1	13:22:56	359	1.7kft	48.1N	11.3E	13:25:59	359	1.7kft	48.1N	11.3E	
T/O	13:28:00	359	1.7kft	48.1N	11.3E						
jw/nevz zero	13:32:48	359	7.0kft	48.0N	11.0E						
lwr bbr	13:33:31	359	7.0kft	48.0N	11.0E						exposed
Profile 1	13:38:26	359	6.9kft	48.0N	10.5E	13:41:19	359	3.9kft	48.0N	10.2E	
Run 1.1	13:42:20	359	3.9kft	48.0N	10.2E	13:52:36	359	3.9kft	48.6N	10.4E	
Run 1.2	13:55:57	359	3.9kft	48.6N	10.4E	14:06:08	359	3.9kft	48.0N	10.2E	
Profile 2	14:06:08	359	3.9kft	48.0N	10.2E	14:07:11	359	4.9kft	48.0N	10.2E	
Profile 2	14:09:13	359	4.8kft	48.0N	10.3E	14:10:23	359	6.0kft	48.0N	10.3E	
Run 2.1	14:10:23	359	6.0kft	48.0N	10.3E	14:21:21	359	6.0kft	48.7N	10.4E	
Run 2.1	14:10:59	359	6.0kft	48.1N	10.2E						start
Run 2.2	14:24:04	359	6.0kft	48.8N	10.4E	14:34:13	359	6.0kft	48.1N	10.3E	
Profile 3	14:36:06	359	6.0kft	48.1N	10.3E	14:43:54	359	14.0kft	48.6N	10.4E	
Profile 3	14:45:27	359	14.0kft	48.6N	10.3E	14:46:39	359	15.0kft	48.5N	10.3E	resume
Run 3.1	14:46:40	359	15.0kft	48.5N	10.3E	14:56:34	359	15.0kft	47.8N	10.2E	
jw nevz zero	14:49:10	359	15.0kft	48.3N	10.3E						
Profile 4	14:59:51	359	15.0kft	47.9N	10.3E						

End P4 FL200

Spike in O3 signal

FL200

New plot, same times

Flight B364 15:09:21
Heading 302 deg Speed 279 knots Height 20.0kft Press 465mb
Lat 48°30.0'N Long 10°0.0'E Wind 143 ms-1/ 359 deg
Temp -25.56C Dewpoint -35.32C
From 13:07:08 to now

Current values
 — TIME FROM MIDNIGHT 54561 secs All sc
 — PRESSURE HEIGHT 20.01 Kft

New plot, same times

Flight B364 15:09:56
Heading 303 deg Speed 279 knots Height 20.0kft Press 465mb
Lat 48°30.0'N Long 10°0.0'E Wind 143 ms-1/ 359 deg
Temp -25.53C Dewpoint -35.91C
From 13:05:31 to now

Current values
 — TIME FROM MIDNIGHT 54594 secs All sc
 — CNC COUNTS 298 p cm-3

R4.1 FL200

Flight B364 15:21:45
Heading 121 deg Speed 260 knots Height 20.0kft Press 465mb
Lat 48°0.0'N Long 10°48.0'E Wind 134 ms/1/359 deg
Temp -25.97C Dewpoint -29.25C
From start to now

Current values
+ + + + STATIC PRESSURE 465.51 mb
+ + + + DEICED TRUE AIR TEMP -25.97 deg C
+ + + + DEW POINT -29.25 deg C

Plot - Microsoft Internet Explorer

Flight B364 15:22:06
 Heading 121 deg Speed 259 knots Height 20.0kft Press 465mb
 Lat 48°0.0'N Long 10°54.0'E Wind 133 ms-1/ 359 deg
 Temp -25.97C Dewpoint -28.86C

Tephigram From: start To: now -

plot parameters as Tephigram

Press 576.STATIC PRESSURE (mb)

523.NONDEICED TRUE AIR TEMP (K)
 524.NONDEICED TRUE AIR TEMP (deg C)
 525.EQUIVALENT POTENTIAL TEMP (K)
 526.REFRACTIVE INDEX (Nunits)
 527.POTENTIAL TEMPERATURE (K)
 528.DRY AIR DENSITY (kg m-3)
 529.DEW POINT (deg C)
 530.VAPOR PRESSURE (hPa)

T1 521.DEICED TRUE AIR TEMP (deg C) Black Cross Del
 T2 529.DEW POINT (deg C) Red Cross Del

End R4.1

R4.2 start + few s

R4.2

Flight B364 15:33:09
Heading 301 deg Speed 295 knots Height 20.0kft Press 485mb
Lat 48°24.0'N Long 10°0.0'E Wind 152 ms-1/ 359 deg
Temp -25.54C Dewpoint -35.34C

T Td Plot From: start To: now -

Save plot parameters as T Td

- 515.TIME FROM MIDNIGHT (secs)
- 523.NONDEICED TRUE AIR TEMP (K)
- 524.NONDEICED TRUE AIR TEMP (deg C)
- 525.EQUIVALENT POTENTIAL TEMP (K)
- 526.REFRACTIVE INDEX (Nunits)
- 527.POTENTIAL TEMPERATURE (K)
- 528.DRY AIR DENSITY (kg m-3)
- 529.DEW POINT (deg C)
- 530.VARIABLE PRESSURE (hPa)

Y1 521.DEICED TRUE AIR TEMP (deg C) Black Line Del
Y2 529.DEW POINT (deg C) Red Line Del

Flight B364 15:34:43
Heading 143 deg Speed 347 knots Height 17.1kft Press 523mb
Lat 48°18.0'N Long 9°54.0'E Wind 178 ms/1/359 deg
Temp -18.84C Dewpoint -26.07C
From start to now

Current values

++++	RADAR HEIGHT	7363.5	ft	☒	All
++++	NEPH BLUE SP	0.15	m-1	☐	
++++	NEPH GREEN SP	2.61	m-1	☐	
++++	NEPH RED SP	0.46	m-1	☐	

Flight Summary B304

Event	Start	Hdg	Hgt	Lat	Long	Stop	Hdg	Hgt	Lat	Long	Comment
Start-Up	13:10:03	359	1.7kft	48.1N	11.3E						
Taxy	13:16:02	359	1.7kft	48.1N	11.3E						
ASP	13:17:11	359	1.7kft	48.1N	11.3E						open
Pirouette 1	13:22:56	359	1.7kft	48.1N	11.3E	13:25:59	359	1.7kft	48.1N	11.3E	
T/O	13:28:00	359	1.7kft	48.1N	11.3E						
jw/nevz zero	13:32:48	359	7.0kft	48.0N	11.0E						
lwr bbr	13:33:31	359	7.0kft	48.0N	11.0E						exposed
Profile 1	13:38:26	359	6.9kft	48.0N	10.5E	13:41:19	359	3.9kft	48.0N	10.2E	
Run 1.1	13:42:20	359	3.9kft	48.0N	10.2E	13:52:36	359	3.9kft	48.6N	10.4E	
Run 1.2	13:55:57	359	3.9kft	48.6N	10.4E	14:06:08	359	3.9kft	48.0N	10.2E	
Profile 2	14:06:08	359	3.9kft	48.0N	10.2E	14:07:11	359	4.9kft	48.0N	10.2E	
Profile 2	14:09:13	359	4.8kft	48.0N	10.3E	14:10:23	359	6.0kft	48.0N	10.3E	
Run 2.1	14:10:23	359	6.0kft	48.0N	10.3E	14:21:21	359	6.0kft	48.7N	10.4E	
Run 2.1	14:10:59	359	6.0kft	48.1N	10.2E						start
Run 2.2	14:24:04	359	6.0kft	48.8N	10.4E	14:34:13	359	6.0kft	48.1N	10.3E	
Profile 3	14:36:06	359	6.0kft	48.1N	10.3E	14:43:54	359	14.0kft	48.6N	10.4E	
Profile 3	14:45:27	359	14.0kft	48.6N	10.3E	14:46:39	359	15.0kft	48.5N	10.3E	resume
Run 3.1	14:46:40	359	15.0kft	48.5N	10.3E	14:56:34	359	15.0kft	47.8N	10.2E	
jw nevz zero	14:49:10	359	15.0kft	48.3N	10.3E						
Profile 4	14:59:51	359	15.0kft	47.9N	10.3E	15:05:10	359	20.0kft	48.3N	10.3E	
Run 4.1	15:05:28	359	20.0kft	48.3N	10.3E	15:22:07	359	20.0kft	48.1N	10.9E	
Run 4.1	15:05:57	359	20.0kft	48.3N	10.3E						started at end p4
Run 4.1	15:12:09	359	20.0kft	48.5N	9.9E						Actual start!!
Run 4.2	15:23:39	359	20.1kft	48.1N	10.9E	15:33:08	359	20.0kft	48.4N	10.0E	

MISSING LOG SHEETS:

The following log sheets are not available for flight B364:

Log	Reason
Pre-flight log	No log available
Mission Scientist 2's log	Awaiting confirmation of whether a log was created by Hugh Coe
Cloud Physics Processing	Processing yet to be completed.
Core Chemistry / TDLAS	no In Flight log except in cases of instrument problems
Filters	Awaiting confirmation of whether a log was created from Keith Bower
2D-S / CAPS / CPI	2D-S / CAPS / SP2 / CPI operator does not create a log sheet
AMS log	AMS operator does not create a log sheet
Dry Neph	operator does not create a log sheet
CVI	no log : CVI was only operated on three flights : B376, B377 & B378

Document control

Revision	Date	Author	Comments
r0	24 Jul 2008	Doug Anderson	Initial version missing the above noted logs
r1			
r2			

VIDEO RECORDINGS:

2 x Forward Facing Cameras

2 x Upward Facing Cameras

Further digital video recordings in avi format:

faam-video-dfc_faam_20080507_b364_133159_1hz.avi
faam-video-dfc_faam_20080507_b364_143159_1hz.avi
faam-video-dfc_faam_20080507_b364_153159_1hz.avi

faam-video-rfc_faam_20080507_b364_133146_1hz.avi
faam-video-rfc_faam_20080507_b364_143146_1hz.avi
faam-video-rfc_faam_20080507_b364_153146_1hz.avi

faam-video-ffc_faam_20080507_b364_133142_1hz.avi
faam-video-ffc_faam_20080507_b364_143142_1hz.avi
faam-video-ffc_faam_20080507_b364_153142_1hz.avi

faam-video-ufc_faam_20080507_b364_133154_1hz.avi
faam-video-ufc_faam_20080507_b364_143154_1hz.avi
faam-video-ufc_faam_20080507_b364_153154_1hz.avi

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